

Unsupervised learning of quadruped robot balance

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Abstract—This paper reports a research activity grounded on year-long experience in unsupervised neural networks used in a lot of different scenarios and here applied to control balance in a quadrupedal robot structure. Simulation results are reported on balance control of a mini cheetah quadruped robot undergoing unexpected weight disturbances coming from additional loads applied on the robot body. The unsupervised learning structure, belonging to the family of Motor Maps controllers, is shown to rapidly learn the additional torques to be applied to the robot legs in order to compensate for the disturbance and so contributing to improve the underlying Whole Body Impulse Controller in front of the robot model uncertainties.

Index Terms—Motor Maps, Reward function, Bio-inspired robots

Legged locomotion is complementary to wheeled one when minimally invasive exploration in unstructured and dangerous terrains and climbing tasks is requested. On the other side, locomotion control is a challenging task to be investigated, and different approaches are commonly adopted for controlling legged robots, requiring different subsystems devoted to handling multiple aspects such as leg coordination, traveling speed, balancing, reflexive behaviours (e.g., elevator and searching reflexes) and others. In our previous works, we highlighted the use of model-free approaches to handle some of the previously introduced domains. One of the adopted architectures was a Motor Map, successfully employed within an action-oriented perception system including weakly controlled chaotic dynamics [1] and for speed control in hexapod robots, also in presence of a *drosophila*-like biomimetic structure [2], [3].

Motor maps are neural structures proposed as an improvement of the more traditional Kohonen self-organising feature maps [4]. These are inspired by the topology-preserving maps identified in the brain, which encode the representation of sensory input signals into space-organised responding units; these, in turn, elicit an action in response to a given input stimulus. Motor maps expand the capabilities of Kohonen networks by adding the possibility to associate to a specific active neuron a required action to be executed [5].

In [1], an action-oriented perception loop was implemented via a bio-inspired architecture using a Motor Map controller (MMC). Perceptual meanings, useful for solving a given task (e.g. a foraging task implemented on an autonomous roving robot), can be autonomously learned, based on the environment-dependent patterns embedded into the controlled chaotic dynamics that are mapped into the robot actions

through the MMC. An FPGA-based implementation of the whole control architecture was also proposed.

In [2], the CPG motor signals for controlling the locomotion in a *drosophila*-inspired hexapod robot, were modulated by the inputs provided by an MMC for speed control, also including reflexive paths. The MMC acts on the CPG by changing the phase displacement between the legs to converge towards stable free gaits able to guarantee the imposed reference speed.

In line with the results previously obtained, an MMC was recently adopted to compensate for attitude control errors in a simulated quadruped platform [6].

In literature, legged locomotion control is designed following a low-level and a high-level approach. The former imposes specific periodic trajectories to the robot legs, the latter is in charge of maintaining other references, such as attitude signals.

Traditional techniques mainly exploit the potentialities of convex model predictive control (MPC) to efficiently regulate the robot attitude while moving in unstructured environments. However, they are based on the knowledge of the analytical model of the robot.

It was demonstrated that the approximation of the complex nonlinear dynamics of quadruped robots through linear time-varying models can guarantee suitability and balance control in experimental environments involving running quadrupeds on flat terrains [7], [8]. However, the performance of the control action heavily relies on the feasibility of the prediction model. For this reason, in the literature, alternative strategies based uniquely on model-free, data-driven nonlinear structures, such as neural networks, were introduced into the control loop. Some examples of this approach refer to reinforcement learning techniques, for improving the capability of attitude maintenance while moving in unstructured environments [9], [10]. The main weakness of this solution is that, in principle, there is no guarantee of preserving stability in the control loop. Moreover, the knowledge of the system dynamics is completely discarded in the controller design. Our approach tries to merge model-based and model-free solutions to maintain the suitability of an MPC, adding compensation in case of unexpected disturbances through an MMC.

The quadruped robot taken into account to evaluate the performance of the proposed controller is the Mini Cheetah robot. It is a torque-controlled four-legged robot developed at the MIT Biomimetic Robotics Lab [7].

For controlling the pitch angle of the simulated Mini Cheetah, the pitch error and its derivative are considered as input signals for the MMC. Therefore, the MMC has two input units and twelve outputs, corresponding to the force components along the three orthogonal axes $f_{i,x}, f_{i,y}, f_{i,z}$ for each actuated leg ($i = 1, \dots, 4$). Fig.1 shows a block scheme of the control loop. The MMC is added, as a parallel block, to the underlying

Fig. 1. The Mini Cheetah control scheme.

MPC. In particular, the leg control commands are generated in two different ways, according to the stance or swing phase of each leg. During the swing phase, the leg trajectory is simply planned using an interpolation of a series of waypoints using a Bezier curve approach. The stance phase is particularly relevant for stability and attitude control and it is realised using an MPC with the addition of a whole-body impulse controller (WBIC) [7], [9]. Here, the MPC computes the forces needed to maintain the body in a standing position, optimised on a $40Hz$ window; then these forces are used as input signals for a faster (i.e., $500Hz$) WBIC, which provides the stabilizing joint torques. During the stance phase, the MMC provides an additional nonlinear feedforward control action, in terms of forces, to be added to the underlying leg joint controller, after being transformed in joint torques $\tau_{i,ff}$ through the Jacobian matrix.

The most important aspect is the self-learning, model-free characteristic of the MMC. This can learn the right control law based on a *Reward Function* to be maximized. Its definition for the proposed application is here reported:

$$Reward = -(\Theta - \Theta_{ref})^2 - \frac{(\dot{\Theta} - \dot{\Theta}_{ref})^2}{(\Theta - \Theta_{ref})^4 + 1} \beta \quad (1)$$

where Θ_{ref} , Θ , $\dot{\Theta}_{ref}$, $\dot{\Theta}$ are the reference and actual pitch, and the reference and actual pitch speed of the robot, respectively. The gain $\beta = 0.001$ was selected.

To assess the reliability of the learning process, a statistical analysis was performed, by running multiple trials of MMCs with a random weight initialization. The results obtained in a typical learning trial, are depicted through the analysis of the Reward function, reported in Fig.2 (a). The corresponding output weight configuration for the vertical component of the output force for one leg is reported in Fig. 2 (b). After the robot learning phase, a test phase was performed in different scenarios involving positive and negative slopes. The robot was able to minimise the pitch error in the different situations

(see Fig. 2 (c)-(d)). It can be noticed that the traditional (MPC) controller alone is not able to compensate for a pitch error due to the presence of an unexpected load (i.e., about 25% of the robot weight) located on the front legs position.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Fig. 2. Effect of the MMC on the pitch control while the robot is trotting: (a) typical reward function trend in a learning trial; (b) final output weight configuration for the vertical force component for one leg; (c)-(d) snapshots showing the robot pitch control when the MMC is active.

The characteristics and advantages of the proposed con-

troller are summarized below:

- The MMC is a reward-based learning controller, uniquely based on data and without needing a model of the robot.
- After the learning phase, a static nonlinear map is generated, representing the robot controller. This implies a real-time, fast control action, much faster than any dynamical controller.
- MMC is intrinsically a model-free controller, suitable to be transferred to other robot architectures maintaining the same strategy. Being a model-free approach, the MMC opens the possibility to be easily transferred to other robotic platforms.
- The MMC action, adds an incremental torque aimed to compensate for disturbances. This preserves the reliability of the underlying MPC-WBIC controller, previously designed and based on the robot model.
- The classical issue to be fixed regard the selection of the MMC structure (i.e. the number of neurons in the Kohonen layer, the learning rate and so on). But the most critical aspect is the Reward function definition which, in general, depends on the error to be minimised.

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